

PARADIGM OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN CONDITIONS OF MODERN GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a study conducted to identify key areas for adapting the regional development paradigm to modern globalization. Research shows that the success of regional development policy in modern times depends significantly on the level of coordinated use of national and international factors and opportunities. It is argued that the improvement of the domestic division of labor, taking into account the comparative advantages of the regions, and the optimization of “world-country-region” relations in relation to their contribution to sustainable and inclusive development can serve as priorities of regional development policy in globalization.

Keywords: regional development, globalization, systematic analysis, paradigm, conceptual recommendations.

Introduction

The actuality of the subject. The regional development strategy currently being implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan aims to ensure the sustainable and balanced development of the country's regions. In particular, it creates a competitive environment based on the principles of sustainable development, social welfare that meets high standards, the formation of a system of environmental security that ensures the efficient use of natural resources and reliable protection of the environment.

Materials and methods

In the article, analysis, synthesis, logical judgment, comparative analysis, and deduction methods were used when analyzing the paradigm of regional development under the conditions of globalization. The information base of the research is made up of official data of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ministry of Economy and the State Statistics Committee, local and foreign academic publications and reports.

The five-year state programs adopted for the socio-economic development of the regions in the country have radically changed the face of the regions, opened up opportunities for strengthening local development potential, improving the business and investment climate, developing infrastructure and raising living standards. However, studies shows that in addition to the achievements, there are still some challenges in ensuring sustainable and inclusive regional development in the country, including increasing the competitiveness of the economy, innovation activity, decent employment and social welfare, strengthening environmental security[10; 4].

In the current period of intensification of globalization, due to the growing impact of international factors on domestic, including regional development processes, the adaptation of regional development policy, including the methodological paradigm of its planning,

to globalization has become urgent. In addition to highlighting the relevance of the topic, the above was the basis for defining the goals and objectives of the study [11].

The purpose of the study is to identify the main directions of adaptation of the methodological paradigm of regional development policy to the conditions of globalization based on the study of the effects of globalization on the driving forces of regional development and to develop recommendations for improving regional development policy in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Due to the intensification of globalization in modern times, the paradigm of regional development needs to take into account the growing influence of international factors on domestic processes and the driving forces of regional development[1].

It can be concluded that in the context of globalization, the “region” is not only a subject with its own interests in the system of “world-country-region” relations, but also a complex subsystem characterized by the interaction and influence of the trinity of economy, society and nature at the regional level. This shows that determining the direction of adaptation of the regional development paradigm to the conditions of globalization requires a multifaceted and multilevel research, which can be possible only on the basis of a systematic analysis approach. Thus, it was considered expedient to conduct the research on the basis of systematic analysis. The research began with a review of the evolutionary history of the regional development paradigm based on the historical-evolutionary method.

On the basis of comparative analysis and generalization, the main features of the paradigm of regional development at the present stage were revealed, and the tendencies of changing the driving forces of regional development under the influence of globalization were studied through systematic analysis. Based on the results obtained, the directions of adapting the regional development paradigm to the conditions of globalization were identified[8; 9].

Studies shows that the evolution of the paradigm of regional development has been accompanied by the deepening and expansion of knowledge about the region as an object of study. As a result, regional development theories now see the region's system of public relations as a subject with its own interests, the region as a multifunctional and multifaceted system, and the emergence of more comprehensive theories[5; 6; 2; 7].

It is clear from the visual description of the structure of regional development factors in the context of

globalization (Table 1.) that each of the upper level factors also affects the lower levels. In other words, these factors combine in a system of “world-country-region” relations and affect each other. Therefore, it is important to link policy measures (plans) appropriate to each territorial level with policy measures (plans) implemented and prepared at other territorial levels when formulating relevant plans for regional development policy.

Table 1

Distribution of regional development factors by territorial levels

	Area levels	Scope
International factors	Global	The world as a whole
	Regional unity	Regions of the world
	Bilateral cooperation	Countries cooperating bilaterally
National factors	Country	The country as a whole
	Region	Economic region, megalopolis and autonomous administrative territories
	District	Administrative districts and cities
	Local	Settlements and villages

Source: Table of theoretical foundations [3; 9; 16] was compiled by the author on the basis of generalization.

It should be noted that although the current approach to regional policy prevails in the world practice, the post-Keynesian theory, which assumes that the unregulated market can erase interregional differences by stimulating the flow of investment to weak regions, and other such theories. views are also used. In many countries, regional policy focuses more on “problem areas”. That is, regional policy is based on the theory of unbalanced development.

Result

As a result of the study, the directions of adaptation of the regional development paradigm to the conditions of globalization were identified, the features of formation and implementation of regional development policy were analyzed and evaluated, and on this basis conceptual recommendations on adaptation of regional development policy and its planning system to globalization were developed. It is argued that in the current era of intensified globalization, improving the domestic division of labor, taking into account the comparative advantages of regions in the country and international division of labor, and optimizing “world-country-region” relations to contribute to sustainable and inclusive development can be regional development policy priorities.

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